

OCCURRENCE OF AURAPTENE, UMBELLIFERONE, MARMIN, LUPEOL AND SKIMMIANINE IN THE ROOT OF *AEGLE MARMELOS* CORREA

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From the root of *Aegle marmelos* Corréa lupeol, skimmianine and three benzo- α -pyrone derivatives, viz., auraptene (geranylumbelliferone), marmin [7-(3:7-dihydroxy-3:7-dimethyloxyloxy)-coumarin] and umbelliferone, have been isolated. This is the first isolation of auraptene in this plant.

From the root of *Aegle marmelos* (Fam. Rutaceæ), a well-known medicinal plant of India, auraptene (geranylumbelliferone), marmin [7-(3:7-dihydroxy-3:7-dimethyloxyloxy)-coumarin], umbelliferone, skimmianine [(2,3-b)-4:7:8-trimethoxyfuroquinoline] and a triterpenoid alcohol, lupeol, have been isolated in good yields. The occurrence of these crystalline compounds, excepting auraptene and lupeol, has been observed earlier in the stem-bark of this plant (Chatterjee *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 606; *Naturwiss.*, 1955, 42, 512; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1922) but in poor yields. Of all these products, the yield of marmin in the root has been found to be remarkably high (*vide infra*). The various parts of this plant, viz., fruits (Dikshit and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 579; Späth *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 1021; Chatterjee and Saha, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 228), leaves (Chatterjee and Bose, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 425; Chatterjee and Roy, *Science & Culture*, 1957, 23, 106; Chakravarty and Das Gupta, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 194; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1580; Chatterjee, Bose and Srimani, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 24, 687), stem-bark (Mookerjee, *Curr. Sci.*, 1943, 12, 209; Chakravarty, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 401; Chatterjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) and heart-wood (Chatterjee and Roy, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 267) have been examined chemically, but not the root. The present report is concerned with the results of our investigations on the root of *A. marmelos*.

Ether extract of the plant materials, collected locally, was separated into hydrochloric acid-soluble portion (A), alkali-soluble fraction (B) and a neutral component (C). The portion (C) on concentration and keeping in a refrigerator for a week deposited marmin, $C_{19}H_{26}O_5$, m.p. 124°. The mother-liquor left after removal of marmin (from C) on chromatography over alumina furnished auraptene (geranylumbelliferone), m.p. 71-72° and a triterpenoid alcohol, m.p. 212°, showing the positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction (pink). The latter has been proved to be identical with lupeol ($C_{30}H_{50}O$) by mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample, by comparison of their spectral measurements, specific rotation data and mixed chromatogram. A further quantity of marmin was obtained from the column by washing it with ethyl acetate.

The basic fraction (A) yielded an alkaloid, m.p. 176°, identified as skimmianine [(2,3-b)-4:7:8-trimethoxyfuroquinoline] by its analyses and mixed m.p. (undepressed) determination with an authentic sample of the alkaloid. The portion (B) on acidification with hydrochloric acid (pH 4-5) yielded umbelliferone, $C_9H_6O_3$. The yields of the above compounds in the root and stem-bark are shown below.

TABLE I

Constituents.	% Yield from	
	Root.	Stem-bark.
Marmin	1.1	0.08
Umbelliferone	0.1	0.02
Skimmianine	0.1	0.0003
Lupeol	0.0058	Nil
Auraptene	0.0028	Nil

The co-occurrence of chemically related compounds, viz., auraptene, marmin and umbelliferone, in the same plant suggests the following pathway of their biogenesis in the plant cells.

The phenylpropanoid unit (C₆-C₃) arising from shikimic acid *via* prephenic acid and phenylalanine (Birch, *Fort. der Chemie org. Naturstoffe*, 1957, 14, 186) is considered to be the logical precursor of coumarins in Nature. The propanoid unit so formed gives rise to *trans*-cinnamic acid which in turn is transformed into *o*-coumaric acid. The latter is then converted into coumarin. Haworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 448) postulated that *p*-hydroxycinnamic acid is the progenitor of umbelliferone. The support of this hypothesis that coumarins originate from *trans*-cinnamic acid derivatives has been available only recently from the findings of Brown (*Canad. J. Biochem. & Physiol.*, 1955, 33, 948) and of Kosuge and Conn (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1959, 234, 2133). The latter investigators have further demonstrated that shikimic acid is the precursor of *trans*-cinnamic acid.

Based on these findings, the present authors have undertaken the synthesis of marmin (*via* auraptene) under physiological conditions. Umbelliferone, originated from shikimic acid, as stated above, on condensation with geraniol under physiological conditions produces traces of auraptene.

Marmin is supposed to arise from auraptene by the action of peroxidase and reductase. Work in this line is being pursued.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Marmin.—Dried and powdered root of *A. marmelos* Correã (1.38 kg.) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) for 20 hrs. (P). The refuse left after extraction with petroleum ether was soxhletted with ether for another 23 hrs. The ether extract (Q) was reduced to 350 c.c. when a solid (0.25g., m.p. 120-22°) separated. It was collected and washed with the same solvent. The mother-liquor of (Q) was digested with 4*N*-HCl (4 × 100 c.c.) when a basic portion (A) completely passed into the acid layer. The ether layer was subsequently treated with aqueous KOH (2.5%; 3 × 100 c.c.) to remove phenolic components (B). The neutral ether solution was combined with the petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) extract (P; *vide supra*), washed with water, dried over anhydrous powdered sodium sulphate and concentrated to a small bulk (50 c.c.). The latter deposited crystals on keeping in the refrigerator for a week. The crystalline mass, m.p. 120-22°, was collected in a suction and washed with a mixture of ethyl acetate-ether (1:7; 12.04 g.). On several crystallisations from ethyl acetate it formed colorless rods, m.p. 124°, and was identified as marmin from its elementary analyses, rotation and mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample of the coumarin, isolated in this laboratory (Chatterjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, 1959). (Found: C, 68.6; H, 7.5; active H, + 0.76; C.Me, 4.6; M.W., 325. Calc. for C₁₉H₂₀O₅: C, 68.3; H, 7.8; C.Me, 4.5%; M.W., 334). $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 26.85$ (in alcohol).

Reduction of Marmin.—Marmin (0.5 g.) on reduction with LiAlH₄ (0.285 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (30 c.c.) furnished umbelliferone, in poor yield, and an oil with a terpene-like odour, which could not be identified.

Isolation of Auraptene and Lupeol.—The mother-liquor of (C), left after the removal of marmin, was subjected to chromatographic resolution over neutral alumina, elution having been carried out with benzene and with ethyl acetate.

TABLE II

Eluents,	Fractions.	Residue on evaporation.
Benzene	1-2	Oily mass crystallised from methanol, m.p. 71-72°.
..	3-9	Solid, m.p. 146-81°.
Ethyl acetate	10-17	Solid melting at a range 109-23°. Crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 120-22°.

The first two fractions furnished auraptene in 0.0028% yield. It was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 71-72°. (Found: C, 76.35; H, 7.64. $C_{18}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 76.5; H, 7.4%). Lupeol appeared in the latter fractions of benzene eluents. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 212°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 27.9$ (in chloroform). (Found: C, 84.75; H, 11.52. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$: C, 84.5; H, 11.7%.) It gave a pink coloration with the Liebermann-Burchard reagent (yield 0.0058%). Ethyl acetate fraction afforded marmin (1.07g.) which on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate yielded colorless crystals, m.p. 124°.

Isolation of Skimmianine.—The acid-soluble portion (A) was basified with sodium carbonate (pH 7.5-8) and exhaustively extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate for 2 hrs. Solid (1.2g.) separated after the removal of the solvent was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 176°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 5.1; N, 5.30; OMe, 36.1. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N$: C, 64.9; H, 5.0; N, 5.4; OMe, 35.9%).

Isolation of Umbelliferone.—Alkaline portion (B) was acidified (pH 3) with HCl (conc.), kept overnight and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. This on concentration gave an oily mass which was subjected to vacuum sublimation at 155-65°/0.01 mm. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 232°. (Found: C, 66.78; H, 3.86. Calc. for $C_9H_8O_3$: C, 66.67; H, 3.70%).

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